

EFFECTIVENESS MODERN MININVASIVE LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY DURING THE COMPLICATION OF ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS

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Actually: Laparoscopic surgical procedures can today be performed in almost all hospitals and the experiences of surgeons are increasing day by day. Cholecystectomy is especially one of the laparoscopic treatments that many surgical assistants firstly learn and apply. The validity of laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is today indisputable in symptomatic gallbladder stones, other benign gallbladder diseases and early stage malignancy according to certain authors.[1-3] It is already the most common and widely applied laparoscopic intervention today. Acute cholecystitis is an inflammatory disease that generates urgent symptoms with exploration findings such as increased wall thickness of the gallbladder, edema and adherence of adjacent organs along with the omentum. Its most common cause is gallbladder stones. Acute cholecystitis is a serious condition and should be treated. Although laparoscopy was considered contraindicated in acute cholecystitis in the first years of laparoscopy, this opinion lost its validity in a short time.[3, 4]

Today, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is essential in the treatment of acute cholecystitis particularly in all patients who have applied in the early period and can tolerate surgery. Although the rates of complication and conversion to open surgery tend to decrease over time with the increasing experience, they are still among the important problems today. The most important complications of laparoscopic cholecystectomy in acute cholecystitis are the biliary tract injuries and bleeding. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is less prone to injuries to the gastrointestinal wall, greater omentum, and peritoneum during operation [1], which avoids intraoperative hemorrhage and suggests a higher safety profile versus small-incision cholecystectomy.

In this article, **we aimed** to retrospectively present the complications that we encountered in laparoscopic cholecystectomy due to acute cholecystitis.

Materials and methods: for the purpose of verification of mechanical jaundice with different etiology, 66 patients with mechanical jaundice syndrome were investigated in 2018-2020 years. The average age of the patients was 50-70 years. The research was carried out in the clinic of "surgical diseases and intensive care" of Bukhara State Medical Institute in the concentration of I-II - surgical departments of Bukhara branch of the Republican Scientific Center for emergency ambulance.

Results: 43 (65%) out of 66 patients with gall stone disease complication was caused by mechanical jaundice, 100% by choledocholithiasis, 23 (35%) patients by mechanical jaundice BPDP tumors.

Conclusion: Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is candidate to be one of the day case surgeries. It is one of the most performed operations in general surgery clinics with low complication, morbidity and mortality rates especially under elective conditions. Due to the easier access to technology and doctor, gallbladder stones are diagnosed more frequently and surgical treatment is applied. However, although the ease of diagnosis has increased, applications to

hospitals due to acute cholecystitis have not decreased.[7] As the experience of surgeons increases, the rates of complications encountered especially in laparoscopic surgery decrease.[5, 8] Moreover, it is known that if the patient is operated as soon as possible following the start of the complaints, less complication is observed in the patient. In the studies conducted, it has been reported that the operations in the first 72 hours are more comfortable in terms of the surgeon.[9] The most important problem encountered during laparoscopic surgery in patients with acute cholecystitis is dissection difficulty and operative complications that may occur accordingly.[10] In our series, the reason for conversion to open in 3 patients (4%) is completely dissection difficulty and exposure deficiency.

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